

Methods of alignment of economic interests of economic entities as a tool for their sustainable and effective functioning

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Abstract. The article discusses the basic principles for aligning the economic interests of economic entities and provides a conceptual diagram of the process of finding an agreed solution. An economic and mathematical analysis of the problems of alignment of economic entities at different levels of the hierarchical management system and having different criteria for evaluating their activities has been carried out. The alignment task is represented by a multi-criteria optimization model with an ideal point (A. Verzhbitsky model), which can be solved using both formal methods and algorithms that include heuristic procedures. The methodological basis of the work is the Pareto efficiency concept which defines an aligned decision as a compromise of the interests of the participants.

A series of iterative formal heuristic algorithms for finding an aligned solution is proposed, which is a modification of the methods of A. Verzhbitsky and Zeleny implementing possible schemes of approaching the ideal point with the boundary of the Pareto region. The correctness of the heuristic procedures used in these algorithms based on the method of O. Larichev is assessed. The advantages of the developed formal heuristic toolkit are shown in comparison with the existing methods designed to align economic interests in multi-level management systems. They include: the rate of convergence to a compromise decision and consideration of not formalized criteria of economic entities when solving the problem.

Introduction: a system of concepts and a mechanism for aligning economic interests.

The problem of aligning economic interests is one of the classic problems of economics. However, many questions of the formulation and solution of this problem require further research. One of such issues is the methodological basis for aligning the economic interests of entities operating in management systems.

An important stage in the formulation of this problem for a controlled socio-economic system is the classification of types of economic interests in its constituent subsystems. In this case, alignment and inconsistency are distinguished, as well as unidirectionality and multidirectionality of economic interests.

Compatibility of the economic interests of one economic entity with the interests of others may appear both in the form of unidirectionality and multidirectionality (contingency) of interests. The unidirectionality of economic interests presupposes the existence of a community of a number of characteristics: goals, means of their achievement, motives, ways of thinking and behavior. Contingency is characterized by the connection of multidirectional interests and means the possibility of realizing each of them only if their interconnection is maintained [14].

Contradictions in the process of aligning economic interests act as a source of improvement and development of the system of interests [13] and can be mitigated or eliminated as a result of the operation of the mechanism of alignment (see Fig. 1).

Source: developed by the authors

Fig. 1. Conceptual diagram of the process of alignment of economic interests of economic entities

The mechanism for aligning the economic interests of economic entities is formed in the context of a constant change in the conditions of emerging markets and is based on the formation of incentives for alignment, in a special way organizing the mutual relations of subjects, and the basis of a set of tools (methods, techniques, ways, actions) that are implemented through a set of economic, managerial, organizational and legal measures. In this case, both consensus (alignment) and lack of consensus of economic interests are possible [16].

Thus, an effective toolkit for achieving a consensus of interests between participants in the alignment process, as well as the choice of an effective interest complex, as well as a rational set of incentives, promote such interaction between economic entities that leads to an aligned solution and ensures maximum production efficiency [2, 17].

Hence the conclusion that an effective mechanism for aligning economic interests determines the effectiveness of the interaction of the subjects of the managed socio-economic system and makes it possible to find optimal points of “intersection” of state, public and personal interests, which contributes to the stabilization of the entire socio-economic system.

Methodological foundations and research hypotheses

An important trend in the development of modern economic and mathematical research is the use of heuristic procedures in the developed methods and their incorporation into decision support systems [2,18,21]. The role of heuristic procedures is becoming increasingly important as researchers become aware of the limitations and incompleteness of formal models. Therefore, more and more often the development of economic and mathematical tools is based on a combination of formal and informal approaches, in particular - taking into account expert assessments when modeling and attracting decision makers (DMs) to solving a wide range of problems. Despite the significance of this problem, the theoretical and methodological foundations for the use of heuristic procedures (the expediency and validity of their inclusion in economic and mathematical models, as well as their correctness and efficiency) are relatively poorly developed, which determines the relevance of further research.

This article to some extent fills the existing gap. It examines heuristic procedures and methods for combining them with formal methods using the example of inter-level control problems. The specificity of these problems is that the processes of making managerial decisions in them are determined by the economic interests of each of the levels. Thus, the problem of inter-level management can be considered as the problem of aligning the economic interests of the various hierarchical levels of the national economic system. Since economic interests relate to the concepts difficult to formalize (it is usually considered that in the alignment tasks they are given implicitly and are implicitly inherent in the object and subject of management), to adequately reflect the need for heuristic procedures implemented through the actions of DMs. Thus, the economic and mathematical tools used below contain both formal methods and heuristic procedures.

Further, the following hypotheses are adopted for the formal formulation of the problem of aligning the economic interests of various levels.

1. The national economy of any country is a complex multi-level system [1,2,13]. Depending on the formulation of the problem, the number of levels considered may be different. As a rule, there are three hierarchical levels of management: macro (national economy), meso (industry, region) and micro (enterprises and other subjects of this level of management), each of which has its own socio-economic interests.

2. At each level, an optimization problem is solved with an appropriate criterion which is quite simple, but in an approximate version, reflects the interests of the hierarchical link. Since economic interests may not be coincident, and often conflict, the resulting decisions go through an alignment stage. Alignment refers to the process of finding a compromise between decisions made by different levels. The compromise obtained as a result of the process of management decisions aligning (MDA) has: a) an economic advantage for each participant; b) Pareto efficiency, i.e. the decision of any level cannot be improved without deterioration of the decision of another level (at least one) [11, p. 288].

3. To simplify the presentation, the three-level problem of coordinating economic interests can be reduced to a two-level one, the economic and mathematical analysis of which is carried out in the following directions: a) the formulation of the optimization problem of aligning interests with the presence of an ideal point; b) the use of formal methods for aligning the interests of different levels. The further stage of research consists in substantiating the need to involve heuristic methods, assessing correctness in MDA procedures, and developing formal heuristic algorithms for aligning economic interests involving the DMS.

Optimization problem with the presence of an ideal point

When formulating a problem, the following assumptions are accepted.

1. A two-level system is considered, at the top level of which decisions are made based on one integral criterion (national economic effect), several criteria are applied at the bottom level (in this case, two, reflecting the interests of meso- and micro-links).

2. Mainly vertical interactions of two types are considered: a) top-level decisions (selection and correction of the ideal point, as well as the stimulating effect of the penalty function when deviating from this point); b) bottom-level decisions - adjustment of initial decisions. Horizontal links (for example, supply of materials, components of products, investments) are represented by exogenous interactions.

3. It is assumed that the top-level criterion can be reduced to the bottom-level criterion space. Thus, the interests of the top level are reflected in the space of the criteria of the bottom level and characterize the maximum national economic effect in it. This assumption allows the MDA process to be carried out on a single basis - in the language of the interests of the bottom level.

4. The ideal target point, which is the initial proposal of the top level, can be both achievable and unachievable. The latter case is most often encountered in actual practice: the initial decisions of the top level, as a rule, poorly take into account the production capabilities and interests of the lower link.

5. To approximate the offers of the top and bottom levels, the principle of negative feedback is used, realized with the help of the penalty function, whose action decreases with the reduction of the distance (characterized by the selected metric) between the ideal point and the decision of the bottom level.

The basis of the economic and mathematical tools for the study of MDA processes is a standard target planning model, which is a multi-criteria optimization problem with an ideal point reflected in [7,23,25].

In the present work, this model has been modified to consider the specific features of MDA:

1) a variant formulation of the problem is considered, which makes it possible to expand the admissible set of solutions to the optimization problem and causes the mobility of the Pareto boundary;

2) special rules for adjusting the target point are used, prescribed by the alignment process;

3) the concept of a negotiation set is introduced, which limits the area of aligned decisions (for the case of an achievable and unachievable target point).

In accordance with accepted hypotheses, the MDA problem has the form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x \in R_x, \quad x \geq 0, \quad R_x^{min} \leq R_x \leq R_x^{max}; \\ y_i = f_i(x), \quad i = 1, \dots, n; \\ \max = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i^B y_i(x) - \rho \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i^T (y_i^0 - y_i(x))^2 \right\}, \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

where R_x — the set of possible states of the object x , which is not fixed and can vary from the region of the minimum possible R_x^{min} to the region of the maximum possible R_x^{max} values; y_i — the object quality criteria; $\{y_i^0\}$ — the target point in the criterion space; ξ_i^B, ξ_i^T, ρ — the weighting factors that characterize respectively the importance of the values of the criteria y_i , their deviations from the target point $\{y_i^0\}$ and the value of the penalty function $\sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i^T (y_i^0 - y_i(x))^2$.

The solution to problem (1) has an important property: it belongs to the Pareto boundary π in the following sense: $\{\tilde{x}\} \in \pi$, where \tilde{x} — the solution to problem (1), $\tilde{y}_i = f(\tilde{x})$ [23,25]. In this case $\{\tilde{y}_i\}$ is in the vicinity of the target point $\{y_i^0\}$. Next, we study the set \tilde{y}_i , which is the image of the boundary π in the space of criteria and is called the criterion Pareto boundary ϕ .

In problem (1), the alignment process is interpreted as follows¹:

1) in the two-level control system under consideration, the preferences of the top and bottom levels are represented by the coefficients ξ_i^T and ξ_i^B , which are considered known, and the

¹The formal methods used to solve the MDA problem also include other methods for solving multi-criteria problems presented in (Bushenkov, Lotov, 1982; Lotov, 1981; Podinovsky, Gavrilov, 1975; Pomansky, 1983).

coefficient ρ , is also specified, reflecting the conditions of interaction between these levels (the role of the penalty function);

2) the initial proposals of the top level are reflected by the ideal point, which is also considered to be known and can be obtained based on the solution of a certain problem external to problem (1). The point $\{y_i^0\}$ is usually unattainable, i.e. φ ;

3) the economic interests of the top level are represented by the ideal (target) point, the deviations from which in the MDA process should be minimized; the economic interests of the bottom level are determined by the system of preferences ξ_i^B , which defines a certain point of the Pareto boundary φ in the space of criteria y_i .

The peculiarity of the mathematical structure of problem (1) is that it allows solving two independent problems of finding the optimal solutions by the top and bottom levels separately. Thus, for the bottom level, at $\rho = 0$ a decision is determined that best meets its economic interests. For the top level, such a decision can be obtained for $\rho = 1$ and $\xi_i^{B=0}$. This structure of problem (1) allows finding the starting points of the MDA process and solving this problem using heuristic procedures.

The role and place of heuristic methods and their correctness in MDA procedures

The above analysis of the MDA process is based on the use of some formal structures that involve consideration of the economic interests of the participants on the basis of certain mathematical relationships (commensurate with the economic damage arising from deviations from the intended goals and the additional effect caused by stimulating the object). These formal constructions can be quite diverse: the formulation of optimization problems can be modified in a certain way, either by simplifying them or by complicating them [22]. Such formal constructions are a means of theoretical analysis and a convenient language for the description of interlevel MDA processes and can be considered as a conceptual basis for real alignment processes that are too complex in the management practice to be exhaustively described by formal models [24].

For effective implementation of MDA, a combination of formal and informal heuristic methods is needed, as well as the participation of one or more DMs implementing heuristic procedures and considering the complex socio-economic interests of various parties. An important issue is the correctness of formal heuristic methods used in MDA. O.I. Larichev [10] was one of the first domestic researchers of this problem. He carried out the analysis of man-machine procedures (MMPs), which are a combination of heuristic and formal methods implemented with the help of computers.

According to the classification of O.I. Larichev, MMPs can be characterized as correct (easily executable by DMs) and incorrect (difficult to implement and accompanied by errors). The correct procedures include: 1) using a particular class of so-called acceptable operations (A) in the decision-making process; 2) ensuring the convergence of iterations to the ε -vicinity of the extremal value of the implicitly expressed utility function.

Most MMPs used in multi-criteria problems are incorrect. The most stringent is the first requirement: the number of class A operations is relatively small in the overall MMP list. The second requirement is violated most often not because of the structure of the selected final algorithm (iterative process of moving to an extreme value), but because of the sensitivity of MMPs to a possible DM error during these iterations (for example, if DMs did not understand the idea of the algorithm convergence). Thus, unlike the requirements that are usually imposed on formal iterative algorithms for finding an approximate solution (the requirement of process convergence, ensuring a satisfactory rate of convergence, etc.), here the requirements for the behaviour of the DMs are put first.

Fig. 2 shows a diagram of the methodology for studying the correctness of MMPs [10] based on the following hypotheses:

– strict formal proof of the MMP correctness is impossible because of the incomplete formalization of the procedure; a content-rich analysis of the problem is needed. Here the method of analogies and the experience of using such procedures can be applied.;

— Any MMP can be represented as a combination of a finite number of elementary operations (EOs) which can be classified according to their level of complexity and the possibility of their successful implementation using the DMs.

In accordance with accepted hypotheses, it is believed that any EO according to its level of complexity for DMs can be assigned either to class A (acceptable) or to class C (complex) operations.

In class A, there are two types of operations: 1) definitely acceptable (A-1), for which reliable information was obtained about the possibility of their successful implementation using DMs (for example, comparing alternatives by one criterion, qualitative comparison of changes in values by two criteria); 2) indefinitely acceptable (A-2), for which no special studies have been conducted, however, their assessment can be carried out by a logical method using the method of analogies (for example, an operation to streamline the criteria by importance).

Similarly, in class C, definitely complex (C-1) and indefinitely complex (C-2) operations are identified in a similar way. So, C-1 refers to the operation of assigning weights of criteria, and C-2 - determining the marginal (limit) coefficients of the criteria replacement.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the MMP correctness research methodology

The classification of operations performed by DMs allows, on the one hand, forming the correct MMPs, choosing them from class A (and especially from the A-1 subset), and on the other hand, allows a comprehensive assessment of the correctness of the already existing MMPs.

Elementary operations are integrated into blocks of generalized typical operations (GTOs) most often used in various classes of problems. So, for the problems of multi-criteria selection, the list of GTOs includes:

- 1) operations with criteria (GTOs-1) - imply that DMs use type C-1, C-2 and A-2 operations and can be characterized as complex for them;
- 2) operations with the evaluation of alternatives by criteria (GTOs-2) - combinations of

type A-1, A-2 (in rare cases, C-2) operations and those that can be recommended for use in MMPs;
3) operations with the evaluation of alternatives in general (GTOs-3) - depending on the specific problem and competence of DMs they are assessed as complex and indefinitely acceptable.

So, in correct MMPs, operations are mainly used with the evaluation of alternatives by criteria (assuming they are representable as combinations of A-1 and C-2 operations), as well as any other class A operations, and during the organisation of MMPs, A-2 operations are preferable.

Formal heuristic methods (FHMs) with the participation of the DMs

FHMs involving one DM. The most well-known FHMs in multi-criteria problems using the concept of a target point include the following [7]:

1) Verzhbitsky procedure: to implement the procedure, the target point y^0 is set (usually unachievable); a metric characterizing the degree of approximation of the solution in the criterion space \tilde{y} to the ideal point is chosen (in problem (1), the sum of squared deviations $\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i^0 - y_i)^2$ is chosen as the metric). The DM perturbs the target point in an arbitrary way, and then, using formal methods, the region of solutions corresponding to these perturbations is determined. After that, the DM chooses a solution in his area that is preferable from his point of view;

2) Zeleny procedure: the procedure differs from the previous one in that the target point y^0 is chosen in the area of effective (Pareto-efficient) solutions; then a corresponding area of compromise solutions is searched for (as a subset of the area of effective solutions) in which the best solution is selected with the help of a DM. In the event that the compromise solution area does not contain a solution that satisfies the DM, the target point is adjusted, and the process is repeated again;

3) procedure of external branching: the target point y^0 is assigned as unachievable and the corresponding solution x^0 is calculated. If $x^0 \in R_x$, the procedure ends; if $x^0 \notin R_x$, then the DM indicates the number i^* of the criterion y_{i^*} which should be changed at the target point so that it becomes more realistic. After this, a new solution is found that is checked for validity, etc. Thus, in this procedure, the DM approaches the target point to the border of effective solutions.

A disadvantage of the described FHMs is the participation of only one DM who usually reflects in his/her decisions the interests of one of the levels (usually the top one, since the main adjustments of the decisions are associated with a change in the target point). In addition, as proved in [10], FHMs data belong to the class of incorrect MMPs, because they contain operations from class C, implemented by a DM, as a rule, with errors. In particular, a DM has to make decisions on three criteria at the same time (target point and changes in two criteria on the Pareto border).

FHMs involving two DMs. Due to the need to build correct FHMs, the procedures for aligning economic interests proposed by the authors provide for the interaction of two DMs, each of whom makes decisions at its own level of competency. The various negotiation schemes set forth below are a combination of Verzhbitsky, Zeleny, and external branching procedures, considering the differentiation of competencies at different levels of management.

When building this type of FHMs, the following hypotheses are accepted.

1) Not less than two experts participate in the alignment whose activities implicitly express the preference system of the corresponding level of management. Wherein:

–the variant is evaluated both based on formal criteria y_i , and informal (soft) criteria;

–experts make a direct choice of the variant on the set π , i.e. the most preferable point at the Pareto level, which corresponds to the assignment of weight coefficients ξ_i^B and ξ_i^T in problems (2) and (3);

–the formation of a compromise solution is made considering the interaction of DMs of both levels as partners in alignment.

2) The initial target point is considered unachievable, which is in line with the usual alignment practice.

3) The purposeful activity of experts is carried out based on the alignment diagram presented in Fig. 1, and it is believed that the DM decisions take into account some informal criteria

and indirect incentive systems that determine the value of the integral utility function of the lower link.

4) When organizing iterative MDA algorithms, fairly simple mathematical methods and simplified techniques used in the practice of alignment are applied. This is due to the participation in real MDA procedures of such experts as planners, managers, etc., for whom this toolkit should be understandable and well interpretable.

5) In order to simplify the alignment, areas of the negotiation set are selected that are most likely to include an aligned decision (narrowing the negotiation set by iteration). So, in accordance with Fig. 1, the search for an aligned decision is carried out within the negotiation set ϕ^* , and the boundary points A and B, according to the condition of the problem, are not an aligned decision. In the course of the iterative process, the bottom-level decision (point A) is shifted along the criterial negotiation set ϕ^* to point B. Thus, at each iteration j it is necessary to view only that part of the negotiation set ϕ^* , that is to the right of the offset position of point A obtained by the iteration $j-1$.

6) The alignment process is carried out in the criteria space $\{y_i\}$. So, according to previously adopted prerequisites, the calculation of the magnitude of the national economic effect $W(y)$ can be made for each point of the criteria space $\{y_i\}$.

The following are two iterative MDA algorithms involving heuristic procedures, a graphical illustration of which is shown in Fig. 3

Algorithm I. The use of the coefficient γ reflecting the tendency of the top level to compromise.

Step 1. Let the target point y^0 be known and the starting points A and B on the boundary ϕ ($A \neq B$) which define the initial boundaries of the negotiation set ϕ^* be defined. The search for the starting points of the negotiation set ϕ is performed by solving problem (1) with $\rho = 0$. It is possible to adjust the obtained results of the top and bottom levels of the DMs taking into account informal criteria.

Step 2. The top-level DM determines the size of the incentive bonus payment and informs the bottom-level DM about it. The solution is found from problem (1) with $\rho = 1$ and $\xi_i^B = 0$.

Step 3. The bottom-level DM, having considered the conditions proposed by the top level, and also taking into account its own informal interests, shifts the starting point A to the position of point A_1 (since its integral utility function at point A_1 is greater than at point A).

Step 4. The top-level DM finds a compromise decision \tilde{y}^0 on the segment A_1y^0 , connecting the new decision of the bottom level A_1 and the previous target point. This is equivalent to the fact that the top-level DM assigns some compromise weighting factor γ :

$$0 \leq \gamma \leq 1, \quad \tilde{y}^0 = A + (1 - \gamma)(y^0 - A), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\tilde{y}^0 = \begin{cases} y^0 & \text{at } \gamma = 0; \\ \tilde{y}^0 = A & \text{at } \gamma = 1. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. MDA process algorithms with two top and bottom level experts (DM^T and DM^B):
a) algorithm I ; b) algorithm II

It is assumed that the top-level DM has some motives or motivations that lead to the search for a compromise decision on the segment A_1y^0 . For example, the execution of a contract is possible only if the proposals of the parties completely align, and the offers of the bottom level are formed only by one participant, and the top-level DM does not have another alternative.

Step 5. Using problem (1) with $\rho = 1$, $\xi_i^B = 0$ and the value $y^0 = \tilde{y}^0$ a new attainable solution B_1 is found, which is closest to the compromise point \tilde{y}^0 and belongs to the boundary ϕ . Since the area $\square_1\square_1$ is smaller than the initial negotiation set AB , the described process can be continued from step 2 until the proposals of the parties align or they come closer within the specified limits.

In the course of the described iterative MDA process, the top level can also use indirect methods of stimulating the bottom level if the possibilities of economic incentives have been exhausted. For example, to guarantee the bottom-level DM future lucrative contracts, to ensure the priority of deliveries of scarce production resources, inclusion in targeted programs, etc.

Algorithm II. Accelerated counter alignment using the coefficients of the tendency to compromise of the top and bottom levels (γ and d).

Algorithm I assumes that top-level DM can transform the unachievable points \tilde{y}^0, \dots into their corresponding achievable points B_1, B_2, \dots , i.e. problem (1) can be solved to obtain achievable points B, B_1, B_2, \dots . In actual situations, this assumption may turn out to be too strong: the top-level

DM usually doesn't realize well the achievable set of bottom levels. Therefore (as confirmed by the practice of planning) determining on this set the point closest to the target is difficult for him/her. In real MDA processes, points $\square, \square_1, \square_2, \dots$ and target points y^0, \tilde{y}^0 are usually tracked without finding points B, B_1, B_2, \dots

Given these circumstances, the alignment algorithm can be further simplified.

1. Let (like in algorithm I) the starting point A and the target point y^0 be known. The top-level DM generates two decisions: 1) the displacement of the target point y^0 to the compromise \tilde{y}^0 on the segment y^0 ; 2) an incentive offer for the bottom level.

2. The bottom-level DM shifts to point A_1 and informs the top level about this decision.

3. The top-level DM finds a new compromise point \tilde{y}^0 on the segment $A_1 y^0$ and forms a new incentive offer for the bottom level, and so on until the proposals come closer with a given accuracy.

Unlike the previous algorithm I, the alignment scheme of algorithm II does not require determining points B, B_1, B_2 , and the rate of convergence of MDA is determined by the stimulating effect (depending on the given coefficient d for the bottom level) and the degree of compromise (the coefficient γ for the top level).

Distinctive features of algorithms I and II are:

1) the possibility of taking informal aspects into account in decision-making processes, making them more realistic;

2) ensuring the MDA process on a parity basis and achieving the coincidence of the proposals of the parties at its final stage;

3) the correctness of the heuristic procedures being carried out, since at each stage of the algorithms of DMs of both levels, decisions are made either using one criterion (A-1 operations) or for two criteria, but on a pre-built Pareto boundary, which also makes these decisions admissibly complex (A-2 operations).

The disadvantages of these algorithms include, firstly, incomplete consideration of feedback (as a response of the lower link to the control signal of the higher organization); and, secondly, the display in them of the lower link as an inert and non-adaptive element.

A modified version of FHMs for two DMs (accounting for the effect of positive feedback)

The difference between the modified FHM variant and the previously considered FHMs with the participation of two DMs consists in taking into account the additional production and economic opportunities of the bottom level that appeared during the MDA process as a result of the stimulating effect of the top level. Such a stimulating effect may be due to a reduction in tax burden, preferential lending, etc. This means an increase in the development potential of the lower link and leads to a shift in the area of its production capabilities (and, accordingly, the Pareto boundary) closer to the target point. Fig. 4 depicts two iterations of the MDA process, taking into account the feedback effect, on the basis of a modification of algorithm I.

Fig. 4. MDA diagram in a modified version of FHMs

The modified version of FHMs more fully takes into account the capabilities of the lower link, regarding it as a more active element of the MDA process. It also provides an increase in the rate of convergence compared to analogues (see algorithms I and II) but requires at each step the construction of a new Pareto boundary (for example, using the generalized achievable set method) [4].

Conclusion

The considered methods can be recommended for a fairly wide class of problems of aligning the economic interests of various administrative levels. In order to more reliably display all the conditions affecting the MDA process, it is advisable to improve the methods for aligning decisions, considering a combination of formal and heuristic procedures. The proposed methods for aligning economic interests with the inclusion of DMs at various levels make it possible to take into account in the final decision not only the factors traditionally reflected by the formal criteria contained in the models, but also informal aspects that are of considerable importance in the real practice of MDA processes. The proposed methods and approaches to the use of formal heuristic procedures can be used not only in management tasks, but also in a wide class of decision-support problems.

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